

Supplementary Material S2 – Aggregation Logic and Survey Questions

...submitted to the Journal Paper “*Mapping Stakeholder Perspectives for Sustainability Transitions: The Case of Lithium-ion Battery Recycling*” by Rutrecht et al. published at Sustainability Journal of MDPI in 2025.

Table S2.1: Example items, and aggregation logic of the stakeholder questionnaire.

Dimension	Example items	Number of items	Scale structure	Aggregation logic
Opportunities	“Reduce greenhouse gas emissions”; “Improve workforce attraction and retention”; “Enhance process efficiency”	27	Two-dimensional matrix: perceived impact (high/low) × implementation effort (high/low)	Individual impact and effort ratings were normalized and combined into four categories (low-hanging fruits, strategic leaps, incremental improvements, money pits). Aggregated scores were used to construct the opportunity map (Figure 3).
Risks	“Regulatory uncertainty”; “Loss of financing”; “Project failure”	21	Four-point criticality scale (1 = low ... 4 = critical)	Item-level scores were averaged across respondents to calculate the criticality index (c), grouped into low (< 40), moderate (40–44), high (45–49), and critical (> 50).
Barriers	“Lack of resources and funding”; “Complexity of systems”; “Lack of methodological know-how”	32	Five-point Likert scale (1 = very low ... 5 = very high)	Mean values were converted into weighted barrier scores (s_b). Thresholds: very low (< 36), low (36–40), moderate (40–44), high (45–50), very high (> 50).
Enablers	“Investment in R&D”; “Implementation of (green) technology”; “Management mindset and awareness”	23	Five-point Likert scale (1 = very low ... 5 = very high)	Mean values were converted into weighted enabler scores (s_e). Thresholds: very low (< 50), low (51–55), moderate (56–60), high (61–65), very high (> 66). (Table 1, Table 2)
Cross-check ranking	—	—	Open selection of top 5 items per dimension	Respondents selected their five most relevant items within each dimension to validate consistency and capture practical salience. Rankings were compared with aggregated weights to triangulate quantitative scores.

All questionnaire items were derived from the literature-based inventory presented in Tables S1.1 – S1.4 (Supplementary Material S1). Responses were collected using an online survey tool during a project workshop and conference sessions. Aggregation of item-level means yielded weighted scores per dimension, which were subsequently used in the risk–opportunity and barrier–intervention mappings (Sections 3.3–3.4).

Table S2.2: Structure and content of the sustainability relevant stakeholder questions.

Q No.	Question / prompt	Dimension(s)	Response type and scale	Purpose / aggregation logic
Q1	Do you associate the following keywords (items) with successful sustainability management ?	Opportunities (27 items)	Five-point Likert scale (1 = very low ... 5 = very high)	Used to assess baseline awareness of sustainability-related opportunities. Mean values aggregated to identify perceived strength of association per item.; supports construct-validity discussion (Section 3.3).
Q2	Please rate the perceived sustainability impact and implementation effort of each opportunity item identified in the literature.	Opportunities (27 items)	Two-dimensional matrix: impact (1 = low ... 2 = high) × effort (1 = low ... 2 = high)	Combined impact and effort ratings categorized items into four quadrants (low-hanging fruits, strategic leaps, incremental improvements, money pits) forming the opportunity map. (Figure 3).
Q3	From your perspective, select the five most relevant opportunities for your own organization.	Opportunities (27 items)	Multiple-choice ranking (top 5 selection)	Used to validate consistency and highlight perceived salience. Triangulated with aggregated scores of Q2.
Q4	How strongly do you associate the following keywords (items) with the risks of not implementing sustainability management ?	Risks (21 items)	Five-point Likert scale (1 = very low ... 5 = very high)	Used to validate individual prioritization behaviour and triangulate with aggregated opportunity scores; supports construct-validity discussion (Section 3.3).
Q5	Evaluate the criticality of each risk item for your organization.	Risks (21 items)	Four-point ordinal scale (1 = low ... 4 = critical)	Captures perceived presence and awareness of risk factors. Mean values used to identify overall salience of risk themes. Item-level means aggregated into the criticality index (c) ; thresholds define low/moderate/high/critical risks.
Q6	Select the five most relevant risks for your own organization.	Risks (21 items)	Multiple-choice ranking (top 5 selection)	Same purpose as Q3; triangulated with aggregated scores of Q5. Confirms alignment between organizational context and aggregated criticality scores.
Q7	Rate the relevance of each internal barrier to sustainability implementation.	Barriers (32 items)	Five-point Likert scale (1 = very low ... 5 = very high)	Mean values converted to weighted scores (s_b); grouped by threshold ranges into very low, low, moderate, high, or very high categories.
Q8	Select the five most relevant internal barriers for your own organization.	Barriers (32 items)	Multiple-choice ranking (top 5 selection)	Same purpose as Q3. Highlights perceived priority barriers AND Confirms priority barriers used in Table 1. Triangulated with aggregated scores of Q7.
Q9	Rate the effectiveness of each internal enabling factor in supporting sustainability implementation.	Enablers (23 items)	Five-point Likert scale (1 = very low ... 5 = very high)	Mean values converted to weighted scores (s_e); grouped by threshold ranges into very low, low, moderate, high, or very high categories.
Q10	Select the five most relevant enablers for your own organization.	Enablers	Multiple-choice ranking (top 5 selection)	Highlights practical importance of enabling measures and validates their relative importance against aggregated scores.

Table S4 - Basic score for every enabler-barrier pairing

		<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; padding: 0 10px;"> <div style="width: 30%; text-align: center;"> <p style="color: red; font-weight: bold;">Lack of resources and funding</p> <p style="color: red; font-weight: bold;">Complexity of systems</p> <p style="color: red; font-weight: bold;">No (reliable) data</p> <p style="color: red; font-weight: bold;">Lack of know-how</p> <p style="color: red; font-weight: bold;">Establishing Transparency</p> <p style="color: red; font-weight: bold;">Lack of standards and technology</p> <p style="color: red; font-weight: bold;">Uncertainty of effects of measures</p> <p style="color: red; font-weight: bold;">Lack of comparability and frameworks</p> <p style="color: orange; font-weight: bold;">Lack of (green) technology</p> <p style="color: orange; font-weight: bold;">Lack of standards and methods</p> <p style="color: orange; font-weight: bold;">Interdisciplinary</p> <p style="color: orange; font-weight: bold;">Long time horizons for planning</p> <p style="color: orange; font-weight: bold;">Fear of quality loss</p> <p style="color: orange; font-weight: bold;">Inertia and mindset of business</p> <p style="color: orange; font-weight: bold;">Fear of dependence on others</p> <p style="color: orange; font-weight: bold;">Challenge to convert best practices to own business</p> <p style="color: orange; font-weight: bold;">Performance monitoring</p> <p style="color: orange; font-weight: bold;">Lack of risk management</p> <p style="color: orange; font-weight: bold;">Capital in fixed assets (e.g. plants)</p> <p style="color: orange; font-weight: bold;">Easily externalized costs</p> <p style="color: orange; font-weight: bold;">Low-level education of employees</p> <p style="color: orange; font-weight: bold;">Spatial isolation of company</p> <p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">No policy with regard on how to handle trade-offs</p> <p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">Fear of power loss</p> <p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">Social norms and culture</p> <p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">Corruption</p> </div> <div style="width: 68%; text-align: right;"> <p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B1</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B2</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B3</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B4</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B5</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B6</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B7</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B8</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B9</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B10</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B11</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B12</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B13</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B14</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B15</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B16</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B17</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B18</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B19</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B20</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B21</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B22</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B23</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B24</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B25</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B26</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B27</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B28</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B29</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B30</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B31</p><p style="color: green; font-weight: bold;">B32</p> </div> </div>																																				
Barrier	Enabler	Type	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	B6	B7	B8	B9	B10	B11	B12	B13	B14	B15	B16	B17	B18	B19	B20	B21	B22	B23	B24	B25	B26	B27	B28	B29	B30	B31	B32				
E22	Promotion of risk literacy	Cultural	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	2	0	2	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	2	1	0	0	0	1	1		
E21	Stakeholder integration	Strategic	0	1	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	2	0	2	2	2	1	1	0	0	1	2	1	0	1	0	2	1	1	2	1			
E20	Risk management	Strategic	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	1	0	2	2	1	2	2	0	2	1	2	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	1			
E19	Benchmarks	Institutional	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0			
E18	New business models	Strategic	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	2	1		
E17	(Sustainable) Supply chain management	Operational	0	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	0	0	2	1	1	1	1	0	2	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	2	0	1	1	2		
E16	Best practices	Operational	0	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	0	2	0	1	1	0	2	1	2	2	1	1	0	2	2			
E15	Ecodesign of products	Strategic	0	1	1	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	2	2	1	0	1	1	1	0	2	0	1	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0		
E14	Revisoning of processes	Strategic	2	1	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	2	1	2	0	1	0	2	0	1	0	2	0	1	0	0	1	0	2	2	
E13	Evidence-based decision making	Operational	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	2	1	0	2	2	0	2	2	1	2	0	2	0	2	0	1	0	2	2	0	0	0	1	2	2	2		
E12	Use of key performance indicators	Institutional	0	2	2	0	2	1	0	1	2	1	0	2	1	1	2	1	0	2	2	1	0	0	2	2	1	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	1	1	
E11	Internal knowledge and data exchange	Operational	0	2	2	2	2	0	0	1	2	0	2	1	1	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	1	0	2	2	2		
E10	Sustainability policy with set priorities	Strategic	0	2	1	1	2	1	0	2	0	2	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	1	1	0	2	0	2	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	2	0	
E9	Mindset and awareness of management	Cultural	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	0	1	0	2	2	2	2	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	2	1	2	0	1	0	2	1	2		
E8	Promotion of awareness among employees	Cultural	0	1	2	1	2	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2
E7	Established transparency of processes	Institutional	0	2	2	1	2	0	0	1	1	1	0	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2
E6	Establishment of frameworks and standards	Strategic	0	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	0	2	1	0	1	0	2	2	2	2	1	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	2	0	2	0	2	2	
E5	Preference for renewables	Cultural	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	
E4	Financing and resources	Strategic	2	0	2	2	2	0	2	2	0	1	0	1	2	2	2	0	2	1	2	2	1	0	0	2	0	2	0	2	2	1	0	0	1	2	2	
E3	Industry-wide cooperation and network	Strategic	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	0	2	0	1	2	2	2	0	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	0	2	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	
E2	Know-how on tools and methods	Technical	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	0	2	2	2	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	2	0	2	0	0	2	
E1	Invest in research and development	Strategic	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	1	2	2	2	1	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	

■ ...Very High
 ■ ...High
 ■ ...Moderate
 ■ ...Low
 ■ ...Very Low

1st FuLiBatter Workshop - Sustainability Radar

Introduction

The project team of COMET module FuLiBatter is asking for your support in collecting data on the perception of risks and chances of zero waste and sustainability management in your domain. This survey enables a holistic approach to formulate strategies to increase the sustainability in the value chain of lithium-ion batteries with special focus on the sector of lithium-ion battery recycling.

We value your privacy.

All answers are collected anonymously and used for evaluation purposes in COMET module FuLiBatter only.

Curious about the result?

We are happy to share the results with you. You can provide a valid email address for this purpose at the end of the process.

Thank you for your participation!

Your valuable time and willingness to cooperate are precious to us.

Duration

10-13 minutes

For more information on the COMET module FuLiBatter, please visit our project homepage

https://www.k1-met.com/modul_fulibatter or follow us on LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/fulibatter/>

* Erforderlich

Personal data

1

Man *

- Woman
- Man
- Other
- Prefer not to say

2

What is your age? *

- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 54+

3

What is your position and job description? *

4

Do you have work related experience in sustainability or environmental management? *

- Yes
- No

Data on your company

5

Which domain can your company be assigned to? *

- Public sector
- Research institute
- Private company
- Listed company

6

Which industry can your company be assigned to? (e.g. manufacturing, recycling, IT,...) *

7

According to the given definition, is your company or institution considered as micro, small, medium or large? *

Table 1 - SME definition by the EU Commission

Number of Employees/ Turnover	0 - 9	10 - 49	50 - 249	> 250
< 2 Mio. €	Micro	Small	Medium	Large
2 Mio. € - 10 Mio. €	Small	Small	Medium	Large
10 Mio. € - 50 Mio. €	Medium	Medium	Medium	Large
> 50 Mio. €	Large	Large	Large	Large

Legend:
Micro: Blue
Small: Green
Medium: Orange
Large: Yellow

- Micro
- Small
- Medium
- Large

8

How many employees are exclusively involved in sustainability or environmental management in full time equivalents? *

- None.
- < 1
- 1-2
- 3-5
- > 5

Risks and chances of (not) implementing sustainability management

The next section gives a non-structured compilation of **chances associated with** the implementation of **zero waste and sustainability management** reported by literature. This is going to be contrasted by a non-structured list of **risks associated with neglecting sustainability management**.

The goal is to assess the main risks and chances that arise for businesses when applying or desisting from sustainable management over time and to **assess the stakeholder's view on the likelihood and significance**. The next step will be to identify and formulate strategies that enable and accelerate the commitment to sustainable management in specific industrial sectors with special focus on recycling and waste management.

9

To what extent do you agree with the following statement:

The company or institution I work for is already extensively involved in environmental and sustainability issues. *

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Sustainability commitment	<input type="radio"/>				

10

To what extent do you associate the following keywords with a positive outcome (chance) of successful sustainability management? (Part 1 of 5)

*

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Cope with climate change	<input type="radio"/>				
Promote social equity	<input type="radio"/>				
Saving Energy	<input type="radio"/>				
Energy Security	<input type="radio"/>				
Saving resources	<input type="radio"/>				

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To what extent do you associate the following keywords with successful sustainability management? (Part 2 of 5) *

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Secure resource supply	<input type="radio"/>				
Affordable resources	<input type="radio"/>				
Reduction of environmental impacts	<input type="radio"/>				
Waste reduction	<input type="radio"/>				
Reduction of greenhouse gas	<input type="radio"/>				

12

To what extent do you associate the following keywords with successful sustainability management? (Part 3 of 5) *

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Create new business models	<input type="radio"/>				
Create jobs	<input type="radio"/>				
Generate profit	<input type="radio"/>				
Less disposal costs	<input type="radio"/>				
New technologies	<input type="radio"/>				

13

To what extent do you associate the following keywords with successful sustainability management? (Part 4 of 5) *

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Improvement of existing technology	<input type="radio"/>				
Protection of assets and equity	<input type="radio"/>				
Reduce production costs	<input type="radio"/>				
Increase production efficiency	<input type="radio"/>				
Diversify revenue streams	<input type="radio"/>				

14

To what extent do you associate the following keywords with successful sustainability management? (Part 5 of 5) *

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Superior stakeholder relations	<input type="radio"/>				
Sustainable decision making	<input type="radio"/>				
Compliance	<input type="radio"/>				
Human health and work safety	<input type="radio"/>				
Image and PR	<input type="radio"/>				
Attract and keep work force	<input type="radio"/>				
Funding and financing	<input type="radio"/>				

15

In your personal opinion, how would you rate the potential **positive impact** on businesses and the **implementation effort** of the listed keywords for successful sustainability management? (Part 1 of 5) *

	Low effort, weak impact	Low effort, high impact	High effort, weak impact	High effort, high impact
Cope with climate change	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Promote social equity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Saving Energy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Energy Security	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Saving resources	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

16

In your personal opinion, how would you rate the potential **positive impact** on businesses and the **implementation effort** of the listed keywords for successful sustainability management? (Part 2 of 5) *

	Low effort, weak impact	Low effort, high impact	High effort, weak impact	High effort, high impact
Secure resource supply	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Affordable resources	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reduce environmental impact	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Waste reduction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reduction of greenhouse gas	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

17

In your personal opinion, how would you rate the potential **positive impact** on businesses and the **implementation effort** of the listed keywords for successful sustainability management? (Part 3 of 5) *

	Low effort, weak impact	Low effort, high impact	High effort, weak impact	High effort, high impact
New business models	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Create jobs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Generate additional profit	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Minimize disposal costs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Research of new technology	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

In your personal opinion, how would you rate the potential **positive impact** on businesses and the **implementation effort** of the listed key words to successfully address them in sustainability management? (Part 4 of 5) *

	Low effort, weak impact	Low effort, high impact	High effort, weak impact	High effort, high impact
Improvement of existing technology	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Protection of assets and equity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reduction of production costs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Increasing production efficiency	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Diversify revenue streams	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

In your personal opinion, how would you rate the potential **positive impact** on businesses and the **implementation effort** of the listed key words for successful sustainability management? (Part 5 of 5) *

	Low effort, weak impact	Low effort, high impact	High effort, weak impact	High effort, high impact
Superior stakeholder relations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sustainable decision making	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Compliance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Human health and work safety	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Image and PR	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Attract and keep work force	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Funding and financing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To which five chances do you yourself attribute the most (untapped) potential in your company? *

Wählen Sie 5 Optionen aus.

- Create jobs
- Image and public relations
- Attract and keep work force
- Energy saving
- Increase production cost
- Compliance
- Minimize disposal costs
- Secure resource supply
- Sustainable decision making
- Energy security
- Diversify revenue stream
- Human health and work safety
- Cope with climate change
- Protect assets and equity
- Improve existing technology
- New business models
- Research of new technology
- Waste reduction
- Generate profit
- Funding and financing
- Reduce environmental impacts
- Superior stakeholder relationships
- Reduction of greenhouse gas
- Saving resources
- Promote social equity
- Affordable resources
- Reduce production cost

To what degree do you agree with the following statement:
The company I work for should take more action towards sustainability. *

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neutral

Agree

Strongly agree

Call to action

Do you want to point out anything with regard to chances we did not cover yet?

23

To what degree do you associate the following keywords with **risks of not implementing** any kind of **sustainability management**? (Part 1 of 4)

*

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Loss of ability to innovate	<input type="radio"/>				
Loss of know-how	<input type="radio"/>				
Loss of power	<input type="radio"/>				
Liability risk	<input type="radio"/>				
Benefit loss	<input type="radio"/>				

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To what degree do you associate the following keywords with **risks of not implementing** any kind of **sustainability management**? (Part 2 of 4)

*

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Risk to human health and work force	<input type="radio"/>				
Environmental impacts	<input type="radio"/>				
Loss of licence to operate	<input type="radio"/>				
Production downtime	<input type="radio"/>				
Unaddressed deficiencies (org.+prod.)	<input type="radio"/>				

25

To what degree do you associate the following keywords with **risks of not implementing** any kind of **sustainability management**? (Part 3 of 4)

*

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Energy scarcity	<input type="radio"/>				
Non-social behaviour e.g. sabotage	<input type="radio"/>				
Image loss	<input type="radio"/>				
Market loss	<input type="radio"/>				
Project failure	<input type="radio"/>				

To what degree do you associate the following keywords with **risks of not implementing** any kind of **sustainability management**? (Part 4 of 4)

*

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Non-compliance	<input type="radio"/>				
Loss of financing	<input type="radio"/>				
Supply chain failure	<input type="radio"/>				
Increasing costs	<input type="radio"/>				
Uncertainty	<input type="radio"/>				
Dependency	<input type="radio"/>				

How do you personally assess the following list of risks for your company? For a definition of the terms low, medium, high and critical please consult the attached graphic. (Part 1 of 2) *

		SEVERITY „Impact on Business“		
		ACCEPTABLE		
PROBABILITY „Event Occurrence“	NOT LIKELY	LOW	LOW	MEDIUM
	POSSIBLE	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH
	PROBABLE	MEDIUM	HIGH	CRITICAL

	Low	Medium	High	Critical
Loss of ability to innovate	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Loss of know-how	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Loss of power	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Liability risk	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Benefit loss	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Risk to human health and work force	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Environmental impacts	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Loss of licence to operate	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Production downtime	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Unaddressed deficiencies (org. + prod.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

How do you personally assess the following list of risks for your company? For a definition of the terms low, medium, high and critical please consult the attached graphic. (Part 2 of 2) *

		SEVERITY „Impact on Business“		
		ACCEPTABLE		
PROBABILITY „Event Occurrence“	NOT LIKELY	LOW	LOW	MEDIUM
	POSSIBLE	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH
	PROBABLE	MEDIUM	HIGH	CRITICAL

	Low	Medium	High	Critical
Energy scarcity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Non-social behaviour e.g. sabotage	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Image loss	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Market loss	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Project failure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Non-compliance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Loss of financing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Supply chain failure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Increasing costs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Uncertainty	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Dependency	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To which five risks do you personally attribute the greatest potential for future damage to your company? *

Wählen Sie 5 Optionen aus.

- Increasing costs
- Non-compliance
- Project failure
- Loss of licence to operate
- Benefit loss
- Production downtime
- Risk to human health and work force
- Unaddressed deficiencies
- Uncertainty
- Loss of ability to innovate
- Dependency
- Liability risk
- Supply chain failure
- Market loss
- Loss of financing
- Environmental impacts
- Loss of power
- Non-social behaviour e.g. sabotage
- Image loss
- Loss of know-how
- Energy scarcity

Barriers of sustainability management

Barriers to sustainability are ubiquitous in our modern world, hindering progress toward a more environmentally responsible and equitable future. Overcoming these barriers is crucial to ensure a sustainable and thriving world for generations to come. The first step is to identify and assess the severity of their impact with your help.

Internal barriers are barriers within the company's own sphere of influence which hinder them from within to implement or to expand their sustainability management.

External barriers are all barriers that prevent companies from implementing sustainability strategies from the outside and can hardly or not be influenced by companies. They are, however, not part of this survey.

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How do you rate the hindering effect of the following **internal barriers**? (Part 1 of 2) *

	None	Minor	Medium	High	Very High
Lack of standards and frameworks	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of know-how	<input type="radio"/>				
Uncertainty of effects of measures	<input type="radio"/>				
Complexity of systems	<input type="radio"/>				
Interdisciplinarity	<input type="radio"/>				
Establishing Transparency	<input type="radio"/>				
Performance monitoring	<input type="radio"/>				
Spatial isolation of company	<input type="radio"/>				
No policy with regard on how to handle trade-offs	<input type="radio"/>				
No (reliable) data	<input type="radio"/>				
Capital in fixed assets (e.g. plants)	<input type="radio"/>				
(Incorrect) Risk perception	<input type="radio"/>				
Green washing	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of (green) technology	<input type="radio"/>				
Scope and limits of existing methods	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of comparability and benchmarks	<input type="radio"/>				

How do you rate the hindering effect of the following **internal barriers**? (Part 2 of 2) *

	None	Minor	Medium	High	Very High
Lack of risk management	<input type="radio"/>				
Fear of eroding profits	<input type="radio"/>				
Fear of power loss	<input type="radio"/>				
Fear of quality loss	<input type="radio"/>				
Fear of dependence on others	<input type="radio"/>				
Social norms and culture	<input type="radio"/>				
Challenge of information exchange	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of dedication of management	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of resources and funding	<input type="radio"/>				
Awareness and mindset of employees	<input type="radio"/>				
Low-level education of employees	<input type="radio"/>				
Long time horizons for planning	<input type="radio"/>				
Challenge to convert best practices to own business	<input type="radio"/>				
Inertia and everyday business	<input type="radio"/>				
Corruption	<input type="radio"/>				
Easily externalized costs	<input type="radio"/>				

To which **five internal barriers** to sustainability do you personally attribute the greatest challenge for your company? *

Wählen Sie 5 Optionen aus.

- Fear of dependency on others
- Easily externalized costs
- Fear of loss of quality
- Establishing transparency
- Lack of standards and frameworks
- Spatial isolation of company
- Low-level education of employees
- Scope and limits of existing methods
- Interdisciplinarity
- Capital in fixed assets
- Lack of policy on how to handle trade-offs
- Inertia and everyday business
- No (reliable) data
- Social norms and culture
- Lack of know-how
- Green-washing
- Challenge to convert best practices to own business
- Lack of comparability and benchmarks
- Lack of (green) technology
- Incorrect risk perception
- Complexity of systems
- Loss of risk management
- Fear of eroding profits
- Challenge of information exchange
- Corruption
- Long time horizons for planning
- Fear of loss of power
- Uncertainty of effects of measures
- Lack of dedication of management
- Awareness and mindset of employees
- Performance monitoring
- No resources and funding

Enablers of Sustainability Management

Enablers for sustainability are crucial to ensure a sustainable and thriving world for generations to come. The first step is to identify internal enabler within the company's sphere of influence and assess the degree of their positive impact with your help.

Internal enablers accelerate sustainability measures within the company's own sphere of influence.

External enablers are external factors, such as sustainability policies or national regulations, that drive sustainability efforts from outside the company. They are, however, not in scope of this survey.

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How do you personally rate the positive effect on sustainability (economically, ecologically or social) of the following **internal enablers**? (Part 1 of 2) *

	None	Minor	Medium	High	Very High
New business models, e.g. product-as-a-Service thinking	<input type="radio"/>				
Preference for renewable resources and energy	<input type="radio"/>				
Evidence-based decision making	<input type="radio"/>				
Mindset and awareness of management	<input type="radio"/>				
Promotion of awareness among employees	<input type="radio"/>				
Promotion of risk literacy	<input type="radio"/>				
Sustainability policy with set priorities	<input type="radio"/>				
Stakeholder integration	<input type="radio"/>				
Internal knowledge and data exchange	<input type="radio"/>				
Revisioning of processes	<input type="radio"/>				
Established transparency of processes	<input type="radio"/>				
Ecodesign of products	<input type="radio"/>				

How do you personally rate the positive effect on sustainability (economically, ecologically or social) of the following **internal enablers**? (Part 2 of 2) *

	None	Minor	Medium	High	Very High
Industry-wide cooperation and network	<input type="radio"/>				
Establishment of frame-works and standards	<input type="radio"/>				
Know-how on tools and methods	<input type="radio"/>				
(Sustainable) Supply chain management	<input type="radio"/>				
Benchmarks	<input type="radio"/>				
Best practices	<input type="radio"/>				
Financing and resources	<input type="radio"/>				
Risk management	<input type="radio"/>				
Use of key performance indicators	<input type="radio"/>				
Invest in research and development	<input type="radio"/>				

To which **five internal enablers** to sustainability do you personally attribute the greatest driving potential for your company? *

Wählen Sie 5 Optionen aus.

- New business models, e.g. product-as-a-service
- Preference for renewable resources and energy
- Evidence-based decision making
- Sustainability mindset and awareness of management
- Promotion of risk literacy
- Sustainability policy with set priorities
- Stakeholder integration
- Internal knowledge and data exchange
- Revisioning of processes
- Established transparency of processes
- Edocdesign of products
- Know-how of experts
- Industry-wide cooperation and network
- Establishment of frameworks and standards
- Know-how on tools and methods
- (Sustainable) Supply chain management
- (Green) Technology
- Benchmarks
- Best practices
- Financing and resources
- Risk management
- Use of sustainability related key performance indicators
- Investment in research and development

We highly appreciate your feedback. Here is some space for you to make comments, remarks or additions on the survey.

We are happy to share the results with you. Please provide a valid email address that will be used for this purpose only. Thank you!